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DARE TO TEACH SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The future role of engineers is facing a shift in focus, from finding technical solutions to sustainable technical solutions. This shift will require engineers to have a different approach to sustainability and technical development. Introducing the Sustainable Development Goals can be considered in conformity with the more traditional methods of engineering where the goals can be seen as a specification where technology can contribute. This change is not only a challenge for the students but also for the teachers. For many teachers, sustainable development was not a part of their education and is not within their area of expertise. Therefore, many teachers feel uncomfortable about teaching sustainable development and struggle with how to incorporate it into their everyday teaching. Other teachers are experts in sustainable development but not in the specific discipline (here electrical engineering or mechatronics). The students need to learn how sustainable development is connected to their specific discipline. A method to introducing the sustainable development goals in discipline focused courses is presented, as inspiration for other teachers. The purpose was to create an assignment that all students found to be interesting and still not require the teacher to become an expert. The assignment was integrated in two discipline focused courses in the first and second cycle. The course evaluations showed that the majority of the students stated that the course had improved their understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals and the

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direct connection to their discipline was appreciated at both levels and made the assignments considered useful.

1 INTRODUCTION

The changes in society are imposing changes in engineering education. Several aspects need to be incorporated in the education in addition to the engineering subjects. Sustainable development is one of the aspects more recently incorporated. Sustainable development is expected to be important for engineers for a long time and needs to be understood in its context [1]. Incorporating professional responsibility for the public good requires a lot, since engineering education until recently was known to even train students to discard these areas [2]. The value alignment of overbelief in technical solutions is another challenge to overcome [3].

To avoid that sustainability will be a subject that the student forget after the course ended, the topic needs to be part of the disciplinary courses [3]. As consequence of that, the situation of the teachers needs to be addressed. In most cases teachers within a discipline have no or very little experience on how to integrate transdisciplinary subjects into disciplinary courses, which in turn could lead to a negative attitude [2].

There are several barriers identified that need to be overcome [4] to make a successful integration of sustainability in a disciplinary course. The organisational barrier is due to the strict division of teachers into groups and/or departments and the feeling of ownership of certain courses. The academic barrier depends on the teachers' interest of developing their own subject while the engineering barrier is based on the unwillingness to add unquantifiable aspects that do not fit methodology. To overcome the barriers several attempts have been made to design courses for teachers. However, these courses only seem to work for the teachers that need them the least [4]. Therefore, a discussion approach based on contribution of the discipline is suggested here and in [3].

In a disciplinary contribution discussion, students can be more involved and be used as drivers in the process [4]. The discussion based bottom-up approach may also limit the risks associated with use of top-down approaches in an academic research culture [4]. There are several pedagogical approaches to address sustainability in engineering education [5], for example the case-study approach. The approach can be implemented by addressing different angles on a particular theme and then bring the different angles together.

A method based on the bottom-up approach, as in [4] and a case study, as in [5] of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has been developed and tested as teaching activities in two different courses. The teaching activities were developed to ease the introduction of sustainability for both the students and the teachers despite the different goals, to create a win-win situation. The courses were part of one first cycle program (Mechatronics) and one second cycle program (Electric Power Engineering).

The purpose of this paper is to present a method to encourage teachers to dare to start teaching sustainability. The target group is teachers, who will start to integrate sustainability in their disciplinary courses, or pedagogical management who will lead

a team of teachers into a more sustainable approach in otherwise technical disciplinary heavy curriculum.

2 TEACHING ACTIVITIES

The teaching activities in both programs were focused on introducing the SDGs. The first activity was an introductory lecture where the teachers introduced the goals and targets as well as gave some examples related to the discipline. The students were then divided into groups and were asked to select a few goals that they would like to discuss. They were later asked to present the goals they had selected. Based on the goals the students made a literature review and reflection in relation to the contribution of their discipline. Their findings were then presented at seminars to the entire student group for feedback, but also inspiration for other, since there are similarities between the contribution of different topics as well as between different goals.

2.1 Mechatronics

The Mechatronics program is a first cycle program and the SDGs were introduced in the first course of the program. The course is an introductory course to mechatronics engineering and the program. Sustainable development and the SDGs were introduced in two workshops. The first workshop started with the introduction lecture and after that the students were asked to study the SDGs briefly and then point out the goals most closely related to mechatronics. The students were divided into groups and each group was given one goal from the list of mechatronics related goals and one goal not on the list. The groups were then given two hours to divide the two goals between them, study them deeper and prepare a short presentation how each goal can be affected by mechatronics.

In the second workshop the question was reversed. The student groups were given mechatronic systems to study and answer how the system would affect the SDGs, positively or negatively. The results were then discussed in class to compare similarities and differences.

2.2 Electric Power Engineering

The introduction of the SDGs was also made in an international master's program of electrical power engineering with about 50 electric engineering students from all over the world. The subject needed to be re-introduced since the group was very diverse when it comes to sustainability. The activities were a part of a mandatory project course and the topic of the discussion was their specific project assignment, that was different for each group. After the seminar the students were also asked to include their findings in the documentation of their project as a preparation for their master thesis work.

3 STUDENT AND TEACHERS VIEW

3.1 Mechatronics

The workshop concept of introducing sustainability was first used in the Mechatronics program in 2018. That year only one workshop was used. In the course evaluation, several students commented that sustainability was interesting and that they would have wanted to go deeper and discuss more.

In 2019 and 2020 both workshops were used, in 2019 in a classroom and in 2020 in Zoom. Both platforms worked well for the discussions and presentations. All students were engaged in the discussions and showed both interest and insight in the technical solutions and their advantages and disadvantages.

In the second workshop, many of the mechatronic systems were found to raise questions on whatever they would increase unemployment and how the batteries used in the systems were produced. Both questions are later addressed in the program. The ethical question about unemployment is used in an ethical essay and a course about batteries, energy and sustainability is given in the second year of the program.

3.2 Electric Power Engineering

In the Electric Power Engineering program, all students stated that they learned more about the SDGs and mostly they appreciated (> 85 %) the strong connection to their ongoing project. However, it had only a minor impact on their project, probably due to late scheduling of the activity in relation to the start of the actual project. Before the introductory lecture they thought it would be a hard assignment, but they reconsidered later. The students primarily selected the middle goals (4-12) which have more technical focus while the teacher addressed the more general aspects regarding climate and environment (13-16) to challenge the students. It turned out that the students performed at similar level for both types of the goals.

Apart from the introductory lecture the students were very independent and due to different backgrounds of the students in each group they could handle the assignment almost on their own. Most questions could easily be handled with counter-questions as they were asked to reflect and there were not any really right and wrong answers.

4 REFLECTION

The teaching activities were used in two different courses: one first cycle course and one second cycle course. However, as the students in the second cycle course had studied sustainability (but not the SDGs) in their earlier studies, they were given a longer writing assignment and the first cycle students made shorter oral presentations, as the method allows adaption to the level of the students

The required preparations for the teachers are in form of reading up on sustainability, the SDGs on a basic level and identify some basic and easy identifiable examples of contribution. This can be done with support from a colleague or by literature. The

main goal of the activity was to start a discussion and for the students to be aware of the SDGs and how they can be affected by different aspects of the discipline. In those discussions, the teachers' discipline specific knowledge was more important than the expertise in sustainability.

As a result of the discussions and the direct link between sustainability and their discipline, the students became more interested in sustainability and wanted to know more. To fulfill that desire and to help the students gain deeper knowledge it is important to continue teaching sustainability throughout the program. This work can with advantage be done in cooperation with an expert in sustainability. Then the link between sustainability and the discipline will still be visible and the knowledge deeper.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

The results from these two courses show that the interest in sustainability can increase if the introduction to sustainability and the SDGs are made in a discipline specific course by the main teacher in that course, who does not have to be an expert in sustainability. Therefore, the first recommendation is to dare to teach sustainability, even if you are not an expert.

The students often have personal driving forces that the teacher can benefit from. Therefore, do not be afraid to take support by the students and have the students driving the discussions forward.

The introduction in a discipline specific course is a good start but need to be followed up by more specific courses later in the program, where experts in sustainability can interact more easily with students and discipline teachers as the bridge is already started.

The students come with different backgrounds and different knowledge in sustainability and that is an asset. The deeper knowledge of some students and the diversity in background can be utilised in the discussions to get a broader view in the discussion. Let the students be the experts when the teacher is not.

In many discussions, there will be no right or wrong answer. The discussions in themselves are the goal. Therefore, it is important to let the students work with the SDGs in groups and learn from that, rather than from lectures and the teacher.

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